

Sample Name: PVC 1-5 μm

Material: Polyvinyl Chloride

Size: 1-5 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- 67% particles are between 1-5 μm
- Particles have a globular aggregate morphology
- $6.8 \pm 0.7 \times 10^{10}$ particles per gram
- $10900 \pm 22 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- Na, Zr, Ca, P, Si, Mg were the most abundant contaminant, ranging from 180-4000 $\mu\text{g/g}$
 - Ca, Zn and P are present in the stabilisers
 - Fe, Ni, Cr are present due to stainless steel
 - Zr and Y are present due to the milling beads
- Occasional Zr spots also observed with SEM-EDX in a small percentage of particles
- No changes due to milling observed in Raman spectrum
- Cathodoluminescence shows typical PVC spectrum with no evidence of degradation, lower intensity is inherent of PVC which gives low signal

Description of terms

- $D[4,3]$: Volume mean (μm)
- $D[3,2]$: Surface area mean (μm)
- $D[2,1]$: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- $D[1,0]$: Number length mean (μm)
- D_v : Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_N : Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w : Number of particles per gram plastic ($\#/g$)
- A_w : Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm^2/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using *Static Light Scattering (SLS)* provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D_v	D_N	N_w	A_w
6.34 ± 0.10	3.99 ± 0.01	2.66 ± 0.05	1.82 ± 0.05	4.65 ± 0.03	1.46 ± 0.03	$6.8 \pm 0.7 \cdot 10^{10}$	10900 ± 22

Morphology (using *Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)* provided by TNO)

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Element	Concentration
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{Cl}$ (PVC)	99.27%
Na	3915 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Zr*	1205 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ca	816 $\mu\text{g/g}$
P	730 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Si	240 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Mg	179 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Fe	10 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Y	77 $\mu\text{g/g}$
Ni, Cu, Br, Zn, Ga, As	<5 $\mu\text{g/g}$

Raman Spectroscopy (provided by Wessling)